

Models and Structures for Dual Technical and Vocational Education Training: A Comparative Review Study of the German, Swiss, and Austrian Models and their Potential Lessons for Kenya

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ABSTRACT

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) systems are essential for equipping individuals with practical skills, enhancing employability, and fostering economic growth. In Kenya, efforts have been made to strengthen the TVET sector through the implementation of the National Policy on Technical and Vocational Education and Training. However, challenges such as negative perceptions of TVET and limited resources persist. To address these challenges, a comparative study of successful Dual Technical and Vocational Education Training (DT-VET) models in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria was conducted to draw lessons for Kenya. Germany's dual apprenticeship system combines theoretical training in vocational schools with practical training in companies. Switzerland emphasizes practical learning and cooperation between companies and training centers, while Austria integrates apprenticeship and school-based learning, recognizing prior experiences. The study identifies key success factors, including strong industry partnerships, industry-driven curricula, and effective quality assurance mechanisms. It also highlights challenges such as gender imbalances in apprenticeships and negative perceptions of vocational education. To tackle these challenges, potential solutions were proposed, including the promotion of industry collaboration, the development of region-specific curricula, enhanced gender equity, the integration of digital skills, and investment in TVET infrastructure. In conclusion, the study suggests key areas for improvement in Kenya's TVET system, such as advocating collaborative approaches, diversifying the curriculum, and promoting gender inclusivity. By adopting best practices from successful DT-VET models, Kenya can strengthen its TVET system, empower its youth, and foster sustainable economic growth.

Keywords: TVET, Dual Training, Apprenticeship, Collaborative Approach

1. INTRODUCTION

Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) are essential components of a nation's education system, providing specialized skills and knowledge that cater to the needs of industries and contribute to economic growth. Kenya, like many other developing countries, faces challenges in its education system, and enhancing TVET is a priority for sustainable development. Dual Technical and Vocational Education Training (DT-VET) models, found successful in various countries, involve close cooperation between educational institutions and industries, providing students with a balance of theoretical learning and practical experience (Graf, 2016).

The primary objective of this paper is to conduct a comprehensive comparative analysis of selected countries' DT-VET models and identify potential lessons for the Republic of Kenya. The paper will focus on the German, Swiss, and Austrian DT-VET systems due to their proven success and recognition on the global stage. By evaluating the key components, successes, challenges, and lessons learned from these countries' models, this study aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders in Kenya's TVET sector.

Kenya's education system has undergone significant reforms in recent years to enhance the role of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) in meeting the country's economic and labor market demands. TVET in Kenya aims to provide learners with practical skills and knowledge that align with industry needs, thus promoting employability and entrepreneurship. The government has taken steps to integrate TVET into the education system and promote collaboration between educational institutions and industry stakeholders (Technical And Vocational Education and Training (Tvet)Policy, 2014). Presently, the government is trying to adopt dual technical and training models (DT-TVET) models to improve the skill set of people.

DT-VET models are characterized by a combination of theoretical classroom-based learning and practical on-the-job training, providing students with the skills and experience needed to succeed in the workforce. In these models, students spend part of their time in educational institutions and the remainder in real work settings, under the guidance of experienced mentors or trainers. The integration of theoretical and practical learning ensures that students acquire both technical competencies and soft skills, such as teamwork, communication, and problem-solving (Chisvert-Tarazona, M. J., Moso-Diez, M., & Marhuenda-Fluixá, 2022). DT-VET models have proven to be effective in addressing skill shortages and improving youth employability in various countries. By aligning training programs with industry needs, DT-VET contributes to a more skilled and adaptable workforce, which, in turn, fosters innovation, productivity, and economic growth. Countries that have successfully implemented DT-VET systems often boast lower youth unemployment rates and a better match between graduates' skills and labor market demands(USAID, 2014).

Kenya's efforts to strengthen TVET have been reinforced by the National Policy on Technical and Vocational Education and Training. The policy emphasizes the need to modernize and

align TVET programs with industry demands, enhancing the employability of TVET graduates. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of public-private partnerships to bridge the gap between academia and industry, ensuring that training programs are relevant and responsive to changing labor market needs. Despite these efforts, challenges persist, including negative societal perceptions of TVET, inadequate funding, and a lack of qualified instructors. These factors hinder the full potential of TVET in Kenya and necessitate a review of successful DT-VET models from other countries to inform policy and practice (Jane Kiprono, David Chepkangor, Frederick Agengo, Patrick Kere, Susan Keino, 2023).(Andiema & Manasi, 2021). The DT-VET approach has gained global recognition for its success in preparing skilled workers and fostering strong links between educational institutions and industries. In Germany, Switzerland, and Austria, the emphasis on hands-on learning and collaboration with companies has contributed to low youth unemployment rates and a steady supply of skilled workers in various sectors (Thelen, 2007), (Langthaler, 2015) The DT-VET models in these countries are characterized by well-defined apprenticeship structures, industry-driven curriculum development, and continuous quality assurance. Apprentices, under the guidance of experienced mentors, receive practical training that aligns with the needs of specific industries, enabling them to smoothly transition into the workforce upon completion of their training.

The success of DT-VET models in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria has demonstrated the vital role of TVET in promoting economic development. In Germany, the dual apprenticeship system has played a key role in maintaining a highly skilled labor force, contributing to the country's economic competitiveness Switzerland's VET system has been pivotal in ensuring a robust workforce that supports its strong manufacturing and precision industries. Similarly, Austria's apprenticeship system has been successful in sustaining a well-trained workforce that supports its diverse industrial sectors. In all three countries, collaboration between TVET institutions and industries is integral to the success of the DT-VET models. This partnership ensures that the skills acquired by students are in line with the current and future needs of the labor market, reducing skills mismatches and enhancing employability (Graf, 2016; Pilz, 2021; Strebel & Strebel, 2021) The objective of this study, was to assess the Dual Technical and Vocational Education Training Models in Germany, Switzerland and Austria and to draw effective lessons that can be applied to the nation of Kenya.

2. METHODOLOGY

A relevant literature search was sourced from reputable databases such as Scopus, Web of Science Core Collection, and Google Scholar between November 2023 and December 2023 independently on all the databases. Key search words such as dual training, technical training, apprentice, Germany, Austria, and Switzerland were used in combinations and individually, and the subsequent literature was retrieved and stored.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 The German Dual Apprenticeship System

The German dual apprenticeship system is considered a gold standard in TVET and serves as a model for many other countries. The system operates on the principle of combining

theoretical training in vocational schools with practical training in companies. Apprentices typically spend three to four days a week at the workplace and the remaining time in vocational schools. It is characterized by clear roles and responsibilities for various stakeholders. Chambers of Industry and Commerce (IHK) and Chambers of Crafts (HWK) play an essential role in organizing and overseeing the apprenticeship contracts, examinations, and training content. The curriculum is designed in close collaboration with companies, ensuring that the skills taught are relevant and meet the demands of the labor market (Deissinger & Gonon, 2021; Eichhorst, Rodríguez-planas, Zimmermann, & Eichhorst, 2012; Graf, 2016)

The success of the German DT-VET model is attributed to the strong collaboration between industry and government. Chambers of Commerce and Industry works closely with educational institutions to identify skills needs, update training content, and ensure that apprenticeships are responsive to technological advancements (Solga, Protsch, & Ebner, 2014). The apprenticeship system has achieved considerable success in producing a highly skilled workforce and contributing to low youth unemployment rates. The seamless transition from training to work has been particularly effective in addressing skills shortages in various sectors. However, challenges persist, such as the gender imbalance in apprenticeships, with certain trades dominated by one gender. Additionally, the system's rigid structure may not be easily adaptable to the needs of emerging industries and new technologies. Kenya can draw valuable lessons from the German dual apprenticeship system by emphasizing collaboration between TVET institutions and industry stakeholders, Kenya can improve the relevance of its training programs and foster a closer alignment with labor market demands. Establishing clear roles for various stakeholders, such as the government, industries, and training institutions, can help ensure effective implementation and coordination of the DT-VET model in Kenya.(Euler & Euler, n.d.)(Linten, Prüstel, & Woll, 2014).

3.2 The Swiss Dual Vocational Education and Training (VET) System

Switzerland's Vocational Education and Training (VET) system, is renowned for its high-quality training and strong connection to the labor market. The Swiss DT-VET model places a heavy emphasis on practical learning, involving apprentices spending the majority of their training in companies and only attending vocational schools for one or two days per week (Dubs, 2006). It offers a wide range of occupations, allowing young people to choose from over 230 different professions (Ruef, 2019). The country's vocational training system is highly flexible and caters to both traditional trades and emerging industries. Companies and training centers collaborate closely to develop training plans that meet the specific needs of each profession (Malik, 2023) (Bucher & Coenen, 2016).

One of the strengths of the Swiss VET system is its recognition of regional specificities and the needs of local labor markets. This regional approach allows for the adaptation of training programs to address the unique requirements of different industries and sectors in various parts of the country. Swiss VET institutions collaborate closely with industry associations and companies to develop and update training curricula, ensuring that apprentices receive up-to-

date and relevant skills Moreover, quality assurance mechanisms, such as expert examinations, contribute to the high reputation and credibility of Swiss VET qualifications (Eichhorst et al., 2012). The Swiss VET system's strong industry partnerships and flexibility have contributed to low youth unemployment rates and a high rate of successful transitions from training to work Apprenticeships are valued and widely respected in Swiss society. However, challenges include the potential exclusion of disadvantaged young people, who may face barriers in accessing apprenticeships. Furthermore, ensuring equal opportunities for apprentices across different regions and sectors remains an ongoing concern (Strebel & Strebel, 2021).

Kenya can learn from Switzerland's successful VET system, particularly regarding its flexibility and regional approach. By acknowledging the diverse needs of various regions and industries, Kenya can tailor training programs to address local labor market demands effectively. Encouraging closer collaboration between vocational schools and industry stakeholders will help ensure the relevance and quality of apprenticeship training in Kenya(Dubs, 2006; Graf, 2013, 2016; Strebel & Strebel, 2021).

3.3 The Austrian Dual Training System

Austria's dual training system combines practical training in companies with theoretical education in vocational schools. The apprenticeship model in Austria emphasizes the integration of learning in both settings, ensuring a balance between practical skills and theoretical knowledge. The Austrian DT-VET system places significant importance on the integration of apprenticeship and school-based learning. Apprentices spend the majority of their time in companies, where they acquire practical skills, while also attending vocational schools on a regular basis to receive theoretical education (Latina & Ramirez, 2017; Sánchez, 2022). Cooperation between companies and vocational schools is a crucial element of the Austrian DT-VET system. Companies actively participate in curriculum development and training program design, ensuring that the skills taught are in line with industry requirements. This collaboration also facilitates the exchange of knowledge and expertise between educational institutions and companies (Langthaler, 2015; Pauline Musset, Simone Bloem, 2013).

Equally, it offers flexibility to learners, allowing them to transfer between different apprenticeship programs or switch from vocational schools to apprenticeships. Furthermore, the system recognizes prior learning and provides opportunities for individuals to have their previous experience and competencies assessed, enabling them to join the apprenticeship program at an appropriate level (Langthaler, 2015; Pauline Musset, Simone Bloem, 2013).

The Austrian dual training system has been successful in producing skilled workers who meet the needs of various sectors. The integration of practical training in companies and theoretical education in vocational schools has led to high-quality training and successful transitions to the labor market. Challenges in the Austrian system include the need for greater gender diversity in apprenticeships and addressing the stigma associated with vocational education

among certain segments of the population. Additionally, ensuring the availability of a sufficient number of high-quality training places for apprentices remains a concern. Kenya can draw lessons from the Austrian dual training system to enhance its TVET landscape. The integration of practical training and theoretical education, coupled with cooperation between companies and vocational schools, can strengthen the relevance and quality of TVET programs in Kenya. Emphasizing flexibility and recognizing prior learning will also allow individuals to enter the system at different stages and capitalize on their existing skills and experiences.

3.4 Commonalities and Differences

While the German, Swiss, and Austrian DT-VET models share the common goal of providing practical and theoretical training, there are notable differences in their structures and implementation. All three models emphasize the integration of classroom-based education and on-the-job training, but the level of industry involvement, the role of vocational schools, and the flexibility of pathways vary greatly. The success of DT-VET models in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria can be attributed to several key factors. These include strong collaboration between educational institutions and industry stakeholders, well-defined apprenticeship structures, the alignment of training programs with industry needs, and effective quality assurance mechanisms. Additionally, the recognition and value placed on apprenticeships in these countries contribute to their success.

3.5 Challenges and Solutions

Despite their successes, DT-VET models also face challenges. Common challenges include the need for gender diversity in apprenticeships, addressing negative perceptions of vocational education, ensuring equal opportunities for all learners, and adapting to technological advancements and emerging industries. Solutions include promoting equal access to apprenticeships, enhancing career guidance and counseling, fostering partnerships with industry and other stakeholders, and providing ongoing professional development for instructors.

Applicability to the Kenyan Context

The German, Swiss, and Austrian DT-VET models offer valuable lessons for Kenya's TVET system. Kenya can benefit from adopting collaborative approaches between educational institutions and industries, aligning training programs with industry needs, promoting flexible pathways and recognition of prior learning, and addressing societal perceptions of TVET. However, it is essential to adapt these models to the specific context of Kenya, considering cultural, economic, and labor market factors.

Lessons and Implications for the Republic of Kenya

A fundamental aspect of the success of DT-VET models in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria is the strong collaboration between educational institutions and industry stakeholders. Kenya should prioritize forging partnerships with various industries and employers to ensure that TVET programs align with the evolving needs of the labor market (Republic of Kenya, 2019).

Industry stakeholders can provide valuable input in curriculum design, share expertise, and offer apprenticeship opportunities to enhance the practical training component.

Developing Industry-Driven Curricula

The adaptability of TVET curricula to address current and future industry demands is vital. In Switzerland, for instance, the VET system offers a wide array of occupations, allowing learners to choose from diverse career paths (Ruef, 2019). Kenya can draw inspiration from this approach to diversify its TVET offerings, ensuring that training programs cater to both traditional trades and emerging sectors, such as renewable energy and information technology.

Enhancing the Status of TVET

Negative societal perceptions of vocational education remain a challenge in many countries, including Kenya (Republic of Kenya, 2019). To enhance the status of TVET, Kenya should promote a positive narrative around technical and vocational education, highlighting the benefits of practical skills, employment opportunities, and entrepreneurship. Public awareness campaigns, involvement of successful TVET graduates, and partnerships with the media can play crucial roles in reshaping perceptions.

Tailoring Apprenticeships to Regional Needs

Recognizing the diverse economic landscape of different regions within the country, Kenya should adopt a regional approach to TVET. Similar to Switzerland's acknowledgment of regional specificities (Greuter & Wolter, 2016), Kenya can tailor training programs to address the unique needs of local industries. This approach would optimize the relevance of TVET training and encourage participation from employers in various regions.

Addressing Gender Disparities

Gender imbalances in apprenticeship programs are common in many countries, and Kenya is no exception. To promote gender equity, Kenya should actively encourage and support the participation of women in non-traditional fields and provide opportunities for girls to explore diverse career options (Bwisa, 2018). Mentorship programs and female role models in male-dominated fields can play a pivotal role in breaking down gender stereotypes and encouraging more balanced participation.

Integrating Technology and Digital Skills

As industries undergo rapid technological transformations, TVET systems must adapt to incorporate relevant digital skills (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2021). Integrating technology-focused training into TVET curricula can equip learners with the competencies needed for the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Kenya can take cues from Germany's emphasis on digitalization in its apprenticeship training to ensure its TVET graduates remain competitive in the global job market (ILO, 2018).

Investing in TVET Infrastructure and Training Facilities

To deliver high-quality DT-VET programs, Kenya must invest in modern infrastructure and well-equipped training facilities (World Bank, 2018). Investment in TVET infrastructure should be a priority for the government, with adequate funding allocated to upgrade existing facilities and establish new ones. This investment will not only enhance the learning experience for apprentices but also demonstrate the value placed on TVET in the country.

4. CONCLUSION

The comparative study of DT-VET models in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria offers valuable insights for Kenya's TVET sector. These models have demonstrated successful outcomes in terms of providing a skilled workforce, reducing youth unemployment, and fostering strong links between educational institutions and industries. Kenya can learn from the collaborative approaches, industry-driven curricula, and flexible pathways observed in these countries to strengthen its own TVET system. However, it is essential for Kenya to adapt these lessons to its unique context, considering cultural, economic, and labor market factors. Emphasizing industry partnerships, developing region-specific curricula, addressing gender disparities, and integrating digital skills will contribute to a more robust and relevant TVET landscape in Kenya. Furthermore, investing in TVET infrastructure and promoting positive perceptions of vocational education are critical steps in elevating the status and importance of TVET in the country. By implementing the right policies, fostering strong partnerships, and ensuring sustained investment, Kenya can make significant strides in harnessing the potential of DT-VET models to drive economic growth, empower its youth, and meet the demands of a rapidly evolving job market.

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